

Third-Line and Beyond Systemic Therapy in Advanced Esophageal Cancer: A Brief Literature Review

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Introduction

We focus on the treatment options for patients with advanced metastatic esophageal cancer where no established line of treatment exists. This article will explore therapeutic approaches for esophageal cancer beyond the third-line setting.

Esophageal cancer remains a significant global health burden due to its aggressive nature and poor prognosis. Despite advancements in early detection and primary treatment modalities, a substantial proportion of patients progress to advanced stages, necessitating the exploration of effective systemic therapies. First-line and second-line treatments have been well established, often incorporating chemotherapy, targeted therapy, and immunotherapy. However, treatment options for clear third-line therapy remain limited, and the optimal management strategy for this cohort is less clearly defined.

The increasing incidence of resistance to conventional treatments underscores the urgency for identifying novel therapeutic agents and strategies specifically in the third-line setting. This review aims to systematically evaluate the existing literature on clear third-line systemic therapies for advanced esophageal cancer. By analyzing the efficacy, safety, and clinical outcomes associated with various therapeutic regimens, this review seeks to provide a comprehensive overview of current treatment landscapes and highlight potential avenues for future research.

Understanding the therapeutic options available for patients with advanced esophageal cancer beyond second-line therapy is crucial for improving survival outcomes and quality of life. This systematic review will thus serve as a valuable resource for clinicians and researchers striving to optimize the management of this challenging disease stage with a clear focus on third-line therapy.

Aim of the Study

The aim of this systematic review is to comprehensively evaluate and synthesize the existing literature on third-line and subsequent systemic therapies for patients with advanced esophageal cancer. By examining the efficacy, safety, and clinical outcomes associated with various therapeutic regimens, this review seeks to provide a detailed overview of the current treatment landscape. Additionally, it aims to identify gaps in knowledge and potential areas for future research, ultimately contributing to the optimization of therapeutic strategies and improving survival and quality of life for patients with advanced esophageal cancer.

Materials and Methods

Relevant studies were identified by systematically searching electronic databases, including PubMed, MEDLINE, ClinicalTrials.gov, Embase, and the Cochrane Library, as well as abstracts and proceedings from major oncology conferences such as ASCO, ESMO, and AACR. The search was conducted using specific keywords and MeSH terms related to "advanced esophageal cancer," "third-line therapy," "systemic therapy," "overall survival," and "progression-free survival."

Inclusion criteria were prospective randomized controlled trials (RCTs) that assessed third-line and beyond systemic therapies in patients with advanced esophageal cancer. Studies were included if they reported on key outcomes such as overall survival (OS), progression-free survival (PFS), response rate (RR), and safety profiles. Retrospective studies, case reports, and non-randomized trials were excluded from this review to ensure a high level of evidence.

Data extraction was performed independently by two reviewers, who assessed the eligibility of studies and extracted relevant data. Discrepancies were resolved through discussion or consultation with a third reviewer. The primary outcomes of interest were OS and PFS, while secondary outcomes included RR and treatment-related adverse events.

Quality assessment of the included RCTs was conducted using the Cochrane risk-of-bias tool, focusing on aspects such as randomization, blinding, and completeness of outcome data. The extracted data were synthesized qualitatively, and where applicable, meta-analyses were performed to quantitatively summarize the treatment effects. The results are presented in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines.

Current Treatment and Ongoing for Third-Line Systemic Therapy and Beyond in Patients with Advanced Esophageal Cancer

Esophageal cancer is the eighth most common cancer worldwide and the sixth leading cause of cancer-related death. Annually, approximately 604,000 new cases are diagnosed, with around 544,000 deaths reported globally. The two main histological types are esophageal squamous cell carcinoma (ESCC) and esophageal adenocarcinoma (EAC). ESCC is more common in Asia and Africa, while EAC is prevalent in Western countries. The 5-year survival rate for advanced esophageal cancer remains low, around 20%, highlighting the need for effective treatment strategies, especially in later-line settings.

The treatment landscape for advanced esophageal cancer, particularly in the third-line setting and beyond, has been evolving as clinicians seek more effective therapies to manage this aggressive disease. By 2024, a variety of systemic treatment options had been explored, including cytotoxic chemotherapy, targeted therapies, and immunotherapies, though the evidence supporting their efficacy varied.

Chemotherapy

In the third-line treatment of advanced esophageal cancer, chemotherapy agents such as *irinotecan*, *docetaxel*, and *paclitaxel* are commonly used. *Irinotecan*, a topoisomerase inhibitor, has shown modest efficacy in patients who have progressed after prior lines of treatment, often administered as a monotherapy. Due to the limited number of studies, no standard second- or third-line chemotherapy has been established for ESCC. Studies have shown that irinotecan combined with 5-FU can be effective in second-line settings, with objective response rates of 17% and 29%, and PFS of 3.1 and 3.7 months, respectively. However, these studies included mixed histological types, not exclusively ESCC. Other studies with irinotecan plus docetaxel regimens reported response rates of 12.5% to 36%, but the majority involved adenocarcinoma histology. Therefore, the optimal therapy for ESCC remains uncertain⁴⁸.

Docetaxel, a taxane, is another option and has demonstrated some benefit, particularly in patients with squamous cell carcinoma. Paclitaxel is also used and can be effective in cases where other treatments have failed, with weekly administration improving tolerability. Despite aggressive multimodality treatment, the majority of esophagogastric adenocarcinoma (EGAC) cases eventually recur. The median progression-free survival (PFS) for first-line metastatic treatment is about 6 months. Approximately 40–50% of patients are eligible for second-line treatment upon progression. Studies incorporating docetaxel in this setting reveal variability in anatomical locations, histological subtypes, and prior treatments, making it challenging to draw conclusions from single-arm studies. Comprehensive reviews and MEDLINE searches highlight the need for further research to better define effective second-line and beyond treatment strategies for EGAC.

Combination regimens, like *FOLFIRI* (*folinic acid, fluorouracil, and irinotecan*), have also been explored, providing additional options for certain patients. However, the benefits are often limited, and toxicity remains a concern, emphasizing the need for individualized treatment strategies. These agents help manage symptoms and provide disease control, but the overall survival benefit is generally modest.

The combination of **S095033** with *Paclitaxel*, evaluated in the clinical trial (NCT05312372), aims to assess its efficacy and safety as a second- or third-line treatment for patients with advanced or metastatic esophageal squamous cell carcinoma (ESCC). This study represents a potential advancement in managing ESCC, focusing on patients who have progressed after initial therapy. The trial's results will help determine

whether this combination can offer improved outcomes and establish its place in the treatment landscape for this challenging disease setting.

The **ESWN 01 trial** (NCT02319187) evaluated the efficacy and safety of irinotecan plus S-1 versus S-1 monotherapy in patients with previously treated recurrent or metastatic esophageal cancer. This randomized study aimed to determine whether the combination regimen could offer improved outcomes compared to S-1 alone. The trial results could provide valuable insights into treatment options for patients who have progressed after standard therapies, potentially establishing irinotecan plus S-1 as a viable option in the second or third-line setting for esophageal cancer.

Targeted Therapy

Trastuzumab is well-established for first-line treatment in HER2-positive esophageal cancer, showing significant survival benefits when combined with chemotherapy. However, its use in subsequent lines (second and third-line) is less defined. The **T-ACT trial** explored trastuzumab combined with chemotherapy as a second-line treatment, showing some efficacy in HER2-positive advanced cases. Current research is investigating its role beyond first-line, especially in combination with agents like pembrolizumab and other chemotherapies. Despite these studies, there is currently no substantial information or clinical data supporting the use of trastuzumab specifically in third-line therapy for esophageal cancer.

A Chinese Phase II study reported that using apatinib at a daily dose of 500 mg resulted in a partial response (PR) rate of 7.7%, a stable disease (SD) rate of 53.8%, and a progressive disease (PD) rate of 30.8%. The overall response rate (ORR) was 7.7%, and the disease control rate (DCR) reached 61.5%. The median progression-free survival (PFS) was 4.63 months, and the median overall survival (OS) was 6.57 months. These findings suggest apatinib could be effective as a second- or further-line treatment for advanced esophageal cancer⁴⁵. The apatinib study was limited in its evidentiary value due to its single-arm design, meaning there was no comparison group. As a result, while the findings suggest potential efficacy, they are not as robust or conclusive as those from randomized controlled trials. Therefore, more comprehensive studies are needed to validate apatinib's effectiveness in treating advanced esophageal cancer in third-line settings.

Immunotherapy

There is no immune checkpoint inhibitors have gained significant attention in treating advanced esophageal cancer, particularly in later lines of therapy. *Pembrolizumab* has been approved for use in PD-L1-positive tumors following progression after initial treatments, showing improved overall survival and disease control in studies like **KEYNOTE-180**. From 121 enrolled patients (100 men and 21 women; median age, 65 years [range, 33-87 years]), 18 (14.9%) had undergone 3 or more prior therapies, 63 (52.1%) had ESCC, and 58 (47.9%) had tumors positive for programmed death ligand-1 (PD-L1), defined as a combined positive score of 10 or higher assessed by immunohistochemistry. Median duration of follow-up was 5.8 months (range, 0.2-18.3 months). Objective response rate was 9.9% (95% CI, 5.2%-16.7%) among all patients (12 of 121), and median duration of response was not reached (range, 1.9-14.4 months). Objective response rate was 14.3% (95% CI, 6.7%-25.4%) among patients with ESCC (9 of 63), 5.2% (95% CI, 1.1%-14.4%) among patients with adenocarcinoma (3 of 58), 13.8% (95% CI, 6.1%-25.4%) among patients with PD-L1-positive tumors (8 of 58), and 6.3% (95% CI, 1.8%-15.5%) among patients with PD-L1-negative tumors (4 of 63)⁴⁶.

The ATTRACTION-1 trial was an early-phase study that evaluated nivolumab as monotherapy in patients with advanced esophageal cancer who had previously undergone multiple lines of treatment. This trial demonstrated that nivolumab had promising anti-tumor activity and was relatively well-tolerated in patients with heavily pretreated esophageal cancer. It provided early evidence supporting the potential role of immune checkpoint inhibitors in later lines of therapy, paving the way for further research in this area. However, its exact efficacy and place in third-line therapy need more validation from larger studies. *Nivolumab* is, evaluated in the **ATTRACTION-3 trial** as a second-line treatment, has also demonstrated effectiveness, especially in esophageal squamous cell carcinoma. However, there is currently no established third-line immunotherapy for esophageal cancer, and research is ongoing to determine optimal strategies for this setting. Combination therapies and novel agents are being investigated to expand treatment options.

Combination Therapies

Until 2024, there are no established or classical combination therapies specifically approved for third-line treatment in advanced esophageal cancer. While ongoing research explores combinations of immunotherapies with chemotherapy or targeted agents, these combinations have yet to become standard practice in the third-line setting. Treatment decisions in this stage often rely on individual patient factors, tumor characteristics, and available clinical trial data.

Despite these advancements, the optimal approach for third-line and beyond systemic therapy in advanced esophageal cancer remains unclear. The heterogeneity of the patient population, variations in tumor biology, and differing responses to treatment highlight the need for personalized treatment strategies. Ongoing clinical trials and real-world studies are essential to further refine these therapeutic options and establish robust evidence-based guidelines.

This systematic review aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the current treatment modalities available as of 2024, highlighting the progress made and identifying areas requiring further research to improve the management of advanced esophageal cancer in the third-line setting and beyond.

Conclusion

The landscape of third-line therapy for esophageal cancer has evolved significantly, with various treatment options now available to address the challenges posed by advanced and refractory disease. Recent advancements in treatment modalities, including novel chemotherapeutic agents, targeted therapies, and immunotherapies, have opened new avenues for managing esophageal cancer in patients who have exhausted first- and second-line treatment options.

Chemotherapy remains a cornerstone in the management of advanced esophageal cancer, with agents such as irinotecan and paclitaxel demonstrating efficacy in combination regimens. Studies like the **ESWN 01 trial** have shown that combining irinotecan with *S-1* can lead to improved progression-free survival compared to *S-1* alone, offering a promising option for patients who have progressed after previous treatments.

Immunotherapy has also made significant strides, with agents such as pembrolizumab showing efficacy in third-line settings. Trials such as **KEYNOTE-028 and KEYNOTE-180** have highlighted the potential of pembrolizumab to improve outcomes in heavily pretreated patients, particularly those with tumors expressing PD-L1.

The exploration of new agents, such as **S095033** in combination with paclitaxel, underscores the ongoing efforts to enhance treatment efficacy and provide additional options for patients with advanced esophageal cancer. While preliminary results are promising, continued research and clinical trials are essential to validate these findings and refine treatment strategies.

In summary, the evolution of third-line therapy for esophageal cancer reflects a broader trend towards personalized and effective treatment approaches. As new therapies and combination regimens are developed and tested, they offer hope for improved survival and quality of life for patients facing this challenging disease. Ongoing research and clinical trials will be crucial in defining optimal treatment strategies and advancing care for patients with advanced esophageal cancer.

Disclosures

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